

Exam Protocol

Patient Info:

Name: [REDACTED] Sex: M ID: P42356

Patient Position: FFS 23-May-19 12:28:31

Patient Position: FFS 23-May-19 12:31:30

Patient Position: FFP 23-May-19 12:52:46

Accumulated exposure data 23-May-19 13:33:10

Performing Physician: Fiore

Total Fluoro: 00:00:03

A Fluoro: 00:00:03

8.99 μ Gym²

0.3mGy

Exposures: 0

Total: 8.99 μ Gym² 0.3mGy

Total: 8.99 μ Gym² 0.3mGy

